

ANALYZES OF THE FORMATION OF THE SPIRITUALITY OF TEENAGERS BASED ON SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MODERN METHODS

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Abstract: In this study, in the formation of the moral and spiritual state of adolescents new information on the analysis of social psychological characteristics is presented. information collected on the basis of research on the formation of education on the basis of which this study was carried out. The main goals and objectives of our research are to study the socio-psychological conditions of the formation of the spirituality of adolescents and analyze them based on modern methods. we studied the psychological views and approaches of psychologists in this regard. Characteristics of social formation of teenagers' spirituality are analyzed. Results obtained as a result of discussion of pedagogical-psychological features of the research conclusions are drawn.

Keywords: Adolescence, mental state of adolescents, upbringing and education, spiritually mature persons, pedagogical-psychological studies.

Introduction

In these studies, we study analyzes of the formation of the spirituality of adolescents based on socio-psychological and modern methods. Our interest is the correct formation of the spirituality of adolescents and the specific challenges of working with this age group. For example, it is best to observe and describe the spirituality of modern youth by forming concepts about spirituality directly in teenagers. Based on the results of research by experienced Uzbek pedagogues-psychologists on the spirituality of youth, actions aimed at forming the appropriate qualitative methodology for this research are described. The special attention of the research is given from useful information, methodical methods that can be used in the study of the spirituality of young people and adolescents, as well as examples of age-related questions are given as part of the curriculum. . First, we describe the characteristics and characteristics of our informants. Next, we offer a definition of spirituality and a way to put it into practice. We then present and describe the rationale for our study design. As we are currently living in the age of advanced technology and rapid information dissemination, such situations have had a negative impact on the research results. Based on the results of analyzes based on socio-psychological and modern methods of forming the spirituality of teenagers, we are surrounded by

modern social networks and modern technologies. First of all, let's take ourselves as an example, not teenagers. We use mobile phones every day. Just imagine what a person would be like if he spent a day without a phone, television, or radio. Nowadays, most teenagers use the phone freely and have their own personal phones. You may ask how the phone affects the morale and mental state of teenagers. Currently, he widely uses social networks such as YouTube, Telegram, Instagram, and Facebook. Most of the films, commercials and interesting shows are watched by our youth every day on these networks. But not all of them have a positive effect on the psyche and spirituality of young people. Excessive use of the phone is a condition that is often observed in teenagers. Excessive use of the phone has negative effects on the thinking ability of these teenagers (mental retardation). Some teenagers have speech problems. Adolescents who spend a lot of time on the phone develop blurred vision. Telephones, televisions, radios, and all magnetic devices emit a small amount of magnetic field and infrared radiation. But we don't know it and we don't see it. Nowadays, we can have a lot of information through the Internet. Parents should always pay attention to their child's upbringing and education. How does my child use the phone? How does my child's use of the phone affect his studies and mental state?. Of course, this is a valid question. We can use the methods of experienced pedagogues and psychologists to form the spirituality of teenagers. We organized questionnaires among teenagers (30 teenagers, 20 of them boys and 10 girls). Question 1: How many hours a day do you use your phone and which social network do you use the most? Question 2: What do you often watch with interest on your phone and what kind of knowledge do you gain? questions were asked and the opinions of teenagers were listened to. 30% of teenagers use their phones for 7-10 hours a day, most of them use Telegram and watch interesting videos on social networks such as YouTube and Instagram. 50% of teenagers answered that they use the phone 6-7 hours a day. The remaining 20% answered that they use the phone 5 hours a day. How do videos, movies and shows on social networks affect the spirituality of teenagers? It has a negative effect on the psyche of some teenagers, that is, there are many cases of sadness, nervousness, fear and mental exhaustion during adolescence. I do not consider teenagers to be guilty of this. Some parents give their children a phone from a young age. The child can watch cartoons or play games. Parents' ears are calm and their hearts are calm. Small children sit in front of the phone for hours. How true this situation is. Some mothers play music or music from their phone to make the baby sleep. What effects does this have on the psyche of a sleeping

baby? These cases are not interesting to anyone now, are we so indifferent? I cannot say that all the videos that teenagers watch on their phones and the games they play on their phones are useful. The reason is that it has serious effects on the mind, mental development and speech, education, and mental state of teenagers. How does the transition from adolescence to adulthood? Young people use the videos they watch on their phones in their lives or imagine the behavior in the video. I was able to study these situations based on the life of teenagers. Nowadays, there are very few young people who read books and are interested in science. I listened to their views and opinions. The teenagers told me about the books they read. When I talk to a teenager who has read a lot of books, his thinking and intellectual development are good, his speech is fluent and, most importantly, he can think freely. I have great confidence that such young people are spiritual, perfect people and will find their place in the future. When it comes to the period of adolescence, along with parents, teachers are also responsible for the education of children. It is necessary to show them the right way in the education and training of young people, in order for them to become spiritually mature and perfect people in the future. After all, every young person should contribute to the development of our country and the well-being of our nation. We, the successors of the nation, our youth, who are the tomorrow of our country and people, should be educated in the spirit of love for the country. Many opportunities and conditions have been created for young people by the President. It is necessary to make proper use of these opportunities and contribute to the development of our country. We need to introduce new programs based on analyzes based on socio-psychological and modern methods of forming the spirituality of teenagers. We need to strengthen the morale of teenagers using modern methods. I read the work of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, "High spirituality is invincible power". Ideological polygon is mentioned in this work. According to him, it is said that it is the most worrying situation if we cannot protect our youth from ideas and thoughts that destroy their spirituality. It describes the consequences of poisoning the minds of young people. One atomic bomb can destroy an area of 100-200 meters. But they brought the ideas that poisoning the minds of young people with destructive ideas will destroy the whole country and even the whole nation. Analyzing these instructive thoughts, it is necessary to pay attention to the spirituality and upbringing of our youth. My opinion is that forming the spirituality of teenagers and developing their worldview will help them to become the owners of high ideas. Knowledgeable, well-educated

and intelligent young people will never come up with a destructive idea. It is necessary not to be indifferent to their education and upbringing in the social-psychological formation of the spirituality of teenagers. Education and upbringing of teenagers as spiritually mature individuals will be development for our future. In forming the worldview of teenagers, we should put forward highly recognized ideas, glorifying our national values and traditions. We are of the opinion that it is possible to form the development of spiritual consciousness in young people through these modern pedagogical and psychological methods.

Conclusion

In conclusion, based on the results of the analyzes of the formation of the spirituality of teenagers based on socio-psychological and modern methods, it should be our main goal and task to educate young people into a mature generation. We must protect them from the influence of external forces. We need to help them to read a lot of books, develop their spiritual maturity and arouse interest in their profession. In a word, our main priority is to jointly form education and training based on socio-psychological characteristics in the formation of the spirituality of teenagers.

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